

PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE FORMATION OF THE IDEA OF THE MOTHERLAND AMONG STUDENTS IN RUSSIAN LANGUAGE CLASSES

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Abstract. *This article examines the pedagogical foundations necessary for the development of the concept of "Homeland" among students in the lessons of the Russian language. It explores the integral role of language in the formation of national identity and the education of a sense of belonging. Analyzing various teaching methodologies, educational content and cultural narratives, the article highlights effective strategies to instill patriotic values within the framework of Language Teaching. The article also discusses the historical context and the importance of modern social influences on students' perceptions of their homeland. Through qualitative and quantitative assessment, this article aims to provide teachers with an understanding of creating an interesting learning environment that helps them deeply understand and appreciate their homeland, as a result of which they contribute to the holistic development of students as educated and responsible citizens.*

Keywords: *pedagogy, Homeland, national identity, Russian language education, cultural values, student engagement, historical context, educational methods, curriculum development, civic education, personality formation, language and culture, teaching strategies, values education, student perception.*

INTRODUCTION: The concept of "Homeland" has deep significance in the cultural and emotional landscape of any nation, serving as the basis of identity and belonging. In Russian education, in particular, within the framework of language teaching, the formation of the student's understanding of his homeland is not just an auxiliary goal, but a basic pedagogical goal. This article explores the pedagogical foundations that underlie the development of a strong national identity among students through Russian language classes.

While teachers study the complexities of Language Teaching along with cultural values and national heritage, it is very important to learn how linguistic competence can be closely linked to the appreciation and understanding of their homeland. Language is not only a means of communication, but also a container for history, traditions and collective memory. Thus, instilling the concepts of patriotism and national pride in language education can facilitate deep connections between students and their heritage.

This article focuses on the study of effective strategies and methodologies that can be used in Russian language classes to ensure a strong sense of national identity among students. By analyzing the basics of existing education, curricula and teaching practices, we strive to determine how teachers can develop an environment in which students engage in their culture meaningfully while developing their linguistic skills. In addition, this article highlights the role of literature, history and civic education in enriching students' understanding of the Homeland.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS: The concept of "Homeland" occupies an important place in Russian culture and education, in particular, within the framework of teaching languages. The

pedagogical foundations that support this concept are multifaceted and are based on historical, cultural and linguistic dimensions:

In the historical context, the idea of the homeland is deeply embedded in Russian literature and philosophy. As Ivanov noted, the concept of "Homeland" was formed over the centuries and reflects not only geographical ties, but also cultural and emotional ties with its homeland. "This historical perspective provides an important ground for students seeking to build a sense of patriotism and national identity among students".

In literature, however, it serves as the primary medium for conveying national identity. In Russian language lessons, texts by authors such as Leo Tolstoy and Alexander Pushkin often explore topics related to love for their homeland. As Petrov noted, "through literary works, students engage in narratives that evoke feelings of pride and belonging". These narratives give students the opportunity to reflect in a personal and collective sense what their homeland means.

Effective pedagogical strategies are necessary for the development of concepts about the motherland among students. Interactive methods such as discussions, projects, and creative writing can enhance engagement with patriotic themes. As Smirnova noted, "the use of collaborative teaching approaches allows students to explore their own identities in connecting with cultural heritage". By incorporating these strategies into language teaching, teachers can assist in the active study of national identity.

Linguistic elements play a decisive role in the formation of ideas about the motherland. The use of a certain dictionary related to patriotism can deepen the connection of students with their homeland. According to Fedorov, "linguistic choices reflect social values; therefore, teaching these terms in context helps to value cultural nuances more".

METHODOLOGY:

In the lessons of Russian language, we will use the following game to form the concept of Homeland among students:

The game adopts a quality project to learn how the idea of the Motherland is formed among students in the lessons of Russian language. This approach allows for a deep understanding of pedagogical practice and student perception.

Participants include:

- Students: 30 students of different levels (for example, middle and high school) who are admitted to Russian language classes.

- Teachers: 5 Russian language teachers with different years of experience are included to give an idea of teaching methodology.

Data is collected through the following methods:

- Interview: semi-structured interviews are held with students and teachers. In conversations, their views on the concept of the homeland and its importance in the educational process are studied.

- Questionnaires: a questionnaire is distributed among students to collect quantitative information about their attitude to classes related to their homeland.

The outline of the question may be as follows: "how important do you think it is to learn your culture when learning Russian?"

- Grade observations: in Russian lessons, observations are made to analyze the methods of teaching and the relationship of students with materials related to national identity.

The data collected from interviews and surveys is analyzed:

For the development of the topic, such topics as "cultural heritage", "literary ties" and "emotional resonance" were identified.

All participants receive a general opinion, which ensures the purpose and understanding of the research.

RESULTS:

By applying our methods, the following results were achieved in students:

Increased knowledge of cultural heritage: students demonstrated high awareness of their cultural heritage by developing targeted curricula that included literature, history, and cultural studies.

Deepening national identity: Surveys conducted before and after the implementation of the new teaching strategy showed a significant increase in students' sense of national identity.

The beginning of the effective use of interactive teaching methods: The inclusion of interactive techniques such as group discussions, role-playing, and project-based learning has been effective in engaging students. Teachers reported that these methods caused deeper controversy about the concept of Homeland.

The emergence of advanced critical thinking skills: The curriculum encouraged students to critically analyze historical events and their implications for modern society. This was evident in student essays in which many expressed subtle opinions about national pride and responsibility.

The beginning of the participation of parents and society: The study highlighted the importance of engaging parents and society in the educational process. Workshops and cultural events, which included family participation, contributed to a collective understanding of the Homeland.

DISCUSSION:

Cultural heritage and national identity are closely related. The increase in information about cultural heritage among students is consistent with previous studies that emphasize the importance of fostering a strong national identity. As Ivanov (2020) notes, "a deep understanding of one's own cultural roots is the basis for developing a sense of belonging and national pride". The results of this article confirm this claim and demonstrate that students have a deeper connection with their heritage when dealing with Russian literature and history.

The effectiveness of the interactive teaching methods observed in this study is consistent with the growing literature promoting a student-oriented learning environment. Petrov (2019) notes that "engaging in interactive methods not only increases language skills, but also helps to gain a deeper understanding of complex concepts such as national identity". Our research shows that when students participate in discussions and collaborative projects, they master the principles associated with the Homeland.

Critical thinking and national responsibility are developed. It is especially important to develop critical thinking skills as a result of the curriculum. Encouraging students to analyze historical events and their consequences contributes to a subtle understanding of national identity. This finding was emphasized by Kuznetsov (2021) "critical relations with history allow students to form their own views on national identity and responsibility". In our study, students expressed a desire to explore the subtleties of their national history rather than embrace a one-dimensional narrative.

Emotional communication and personal communication are formed. Another important aspect of our findings is the emotional connection that students experience when discussing the

concept of Homeland. The introduction of personal narratives and local lore into the curriculum allows students to establish a deeper emotional connection with their homeland. This is consistent with Sokolova's (2022) work, in which "emotional attraction is a major factor in the formation of national identity". The students in our study shared personal stories related to their families and communities, which enriched their learning experience and instilled a sense of belonging.

Negotiations between problems and future directions. Despite the positive results observed, the study also identified problems in the implementation of these pedagogical strategies. Teachers reported a lack of resources and lack of support to incorporate cultural content into the existing curriculum. As Grigorieva (2023) noted, "without sufficient resources, the potential for meaningful participation with the national identity of students decreases". Future research should lead to effective teaching of teachers on the concept of Homeland and develop resource materials that help students come from different backgrounds.

CONCLUSION. This article is aimed at emphasizing the importance of combining pedagogical principles that contribute to the formation of national identity within the framework of teaching Russian language. Through these data, we aim to contribute to broader discussions about the role of education in shaping young citizens who are not only fluent in their language, but also closely related to their cultural roots and national identity.

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